

Transformation Of Accounting Education In The 4.0 Era, A must Or Not ?

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The 4.0 Era

Many type of work
that will be lost

Impact on
Accounting
Profession

Humans are replaced
by programs

ROBOTS < replacing > HUMANS

How Accountant Profession Facing The 4.0 Era?

The Role of Accountants Will Change Radically

Fluent in Technology

Big Data

How Accountant Responded Era 4.0

Invest in Developing Digital Skills

Implementing Prototypes of New Technologies (while learning by doing)

Education Based on International Certification and Digital Skills

Responsive to Changes in Industry, Business and Technological Development

Curriculum and Learning Based on Human-Digital Skills

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Accounting in the 4.0 era,
needed special Education In
Digital Technology

But... There are several
Universities that still
haven't developed a new
Accounting curriculum

So.. Transformation Of
Accounting Education In
The 4.0 Era is a must.

THANKS!

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